

MONITORING OF SAFETY INDICATORS OF FOOD RAW MATERIALS AND FOOD PRODUCTS**Voronina N.V.,***Doctor of Medical Sciences,
Tashkent Pharmaceutical Institute, Uzbekistan
100015 Tashkent Mirabad district, Aibek street, 45***Shamsutdinova M.A.***Competitor,
Sanitary and hygienic welfare and public health service of the Republic of Uzbekistan
100097 Tashkent District: Chilanzar district, Bunyodkor, 46***Abstract**

The article presents, from a comparative perspective, the results of a hygienic assessment of food safety indicators for food raw materials and food products sold in Samarkand Region (Uzbekistan) in 2020-2021. More than 24,000 analyses have been carried out to detect toxic elements, pesticides and their residues, mycotoxins, nitrates, nitrites and their derivatives, antibiotics, preservatives and colourants, as well as compounds from long-term storage and high temperature treatment of food products. It has been established that food raw materials and food products, in general, meet hygienic safety requirements. On average, during the study period, the number of samples with deviations from the maximum permissible concentrations was in the range of 4.4-6.3%. The most significant number of inconsistencies was found during the testing of table salt (30-33%) and fruit and vegetable products (4-5,7%).

Keywords: safety, food raw materials and food products, laboratory control, hygienic assessment

In the modern world, the problems of controlling the safety of food raw materials and food products are relevant, since food that does not meet hygienic requirements is one of the main risk factors for public health.

It has been shown that it is with food that up to 70% of various xenobiotics with high toxicity enter the human body [5]. According to the Codex Alimentarius Commission (CAC), "food safety is a guarantee that food products will not harm the consumer if they are prepared and/or eaten in accordance with their intended purpose" [3]. The legislative and regulatory framework for ensuring food security has been created and is being improved in the Republic of Uzbekistan [11]. The key element of the system of providing the population with safe food products is the organization of control and monitoring of their contamination [4,10].

The purpose of the work was to conduct a hygienic assessment of the safety indicators of food raw materials and food products sold in the territory of the Samarkand region (Uzbekistan) in 2020-2021.

Laboratory studies of food products and food raw materials were carried out using standard sanitary and hygienic methods and techniques based on the principles of atomic absorption spectrophotometry, potentiometry, high-performance liquid chromatography, and other principles of quantitative analysis methods. The results obtained were correlated with the recommended republican standards "Hygienic standards for food safety" (2019).

Results and discussion. According to the results of laboratory tests, the investigated samples were ranked according to the amount of non-compliance with regulatory data.

Thus, a significant number and continuous annual increase in the number of samples exceeding the normative values (from 30% in 2020 to 33% in 2021) was observed in salt testing for iodine content.

It has been proven that iodine deficiency can lead to iodine deficiency disorders [9]. During pregnancy, there is a risk of spontaneous abortion, stillbirth, birth defects, impaired mental and physical development of the fetus [2]. In adulthood, there is a risk of thyroid disease [12]. Due to the high role of iodine in the formation and maintenance of human health, the law "On the prevention of iodine deficiency diseases" was adopted in the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2007. The law provides for mass prevention of iodine deficiency diseases among the population by eating iodized salt and iodized foods. This regulatory document establishes that iodized salt and iodized food products after the expiration of the established shelf life are subject to recycling, industrial processing or repeated iodization.

Melon crops and fruit and vegetable products were included in the second group of food products, which have deviations from the proper values. In the samples of potatoes, watermelon and melon, excess of the norms for the content of nitrates was revealed. The percentage of deviations in samples ranges from 4.0% in 2020 to 5.7% in 2021. It should be noted that in general, the excess of nitrate indicators was noted in all groups that make up the food chain: soil-plant-animal-human. Of the tested meat products for the presence of nitrates, non-compliance with regulatory data was found in 1.1% and 0.4% of the studied samples, respectively.

The high content of nitrates in plant products is often due to the use of increased doses of nitrogen fertilizers, their use without taking into account the growing season of the plant, species characteristics and varieties, as well as non-compliance with storage conditions. It is proved that the toxic effect of nitrates on the human body is associated with their reduction to nitrites, ammonia, hydroxylamine under the influence of the microflora of the digestive tract and tissue enzymes [7,8].

Increased levels of active nitrogen forms can lead to 'nitrosative stress', in which mediators of damage to

cellular structures, including lipids, membranes, proteins and DNA, are produced [6].

Of the tested 989 samples in 2020 and 1,409 samples of milk and dairy products in 2021, a discrepancy of 3.4% and 2.4% of the tested samples was found. Moreover, of these, more than 60% of the samples exceeded the requirements for the acidity of milk, indicating its stale. Another reason for the "discrepancy" was the detection of sterols of vegetable origin in cow oil samples, indicating the presence of vegetable oil unusual for this product.

Of the studied 2,143 samples of cereals, flour-grains and bakery products, a discrepancy of 1.1% of samples was noted in 2020, but this indicator, with the same number of samples studied, increased by 2.5 times by 2021. As a result of the research, it was found that in 35% of the samples with deviations from the norm, high levels of zinc content in flour were noted. According to scientists, the increased levels of this metal in food products may be due to its high content in the soils where wheat grew [1]. Excessive amounts of the mineral in the body can also lead to severe intoxication, but zinc from grain is absorbed by the human body by only 25-30%.

As part of the monitoring, tests of other product groups and food raw materials showed that all the samples studied met the requirements of regulatory documents.

Thus, the accumulation and analysis of monitoring data on food safety indicators make it possible to obtain quantitative and qualitative characteristics of their contamination levels and assess the risk of its impact on public health.

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